

VERB FORMATION AND EXPRESSION OF ACTION VERBS IN ARABIC

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Annotation: This article provides a semantic analysis of the structure of verbs in Arabic and highlights the types and expressions. The purpose of this scientific work is to analyze and show the results of the formation of verbs and the expression of action verbs in Arabic.

Key words: verb formation, action verbs, types of action verbs, categorization, prophets, connection, concept of action.

INTRODUCTION

Talking about words made from verbs, here is internal derivation from verbs (making verbs from verbs) or derivation outside the verb (from words that are not verbs verb formation) in which neologism (new word) among verbs, denominatives (formation of a verb from a noun) are of great importance. when a verb is formed from the stem of a verb, i.e., in the derivative chapters, Chapters I, II, IV cover transitivity, Chapter V covers passiveness in relation to Chapter II, identity, Chapters VII, VIII, IX cover passive, Chapters III, VI means interaction. It is not optional to create new verbs based on weights in practice, dictionaries have primary and secondary meanings of each chapter. There are two opposing sides in the system of forming words from verbs in the Arabic language, one of which is to perform an action for oneself (self) and to focus on an object or action-action itself. sha means that the object itself performs (inaction). The morphological indicator of identity is the element "t". There are intensive and extensive aspects that form the basis of the verb, and they mean the strengthening

of the action and its repeated occurrence, the mutual performance of the action. The characteristic of intensifying, repeating or prolonging the action belongs to the second chapter. Chapter V was created from Chapter II, and it fully accepted the characteristics of Chapter II, but these characteristics mean that it can perform for itself.

BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

The feature of conativeness (reciprocity) is characteristic of Chapter III. “طارِدْ”- to chase (from “طرد” - "to drive"). Also, in this chapter, some characteristic of the object is shown in the subject's relation to the object. For example: “لاطف”- to have a good relationship (with someone).

If the parts of the verb do not contain prefixes “إست/إن/ت”, they do not mean passive and are called correct verbs. If the parts of the verb are formed using the above prefixes, such verbs are called passive (individual) verbs.¹

Arabic does not have seven conjugations like Uzbek. Arabic language learners know that there are three agreements in this language: subject, subjunctive, and indicative. The remaining meanings of the agreement can be expressed with the help of prepositions.

In Arabic, there are intransitive verbs such as جاء -to come,- ذهب to go, رجع -to arrive, to return, رجع, أتى -to come, قدم -to come. There are intransitive verbs that turn into transitive verbs by adding the preposition ب before the word denoting the object of the action.² By this way, they become a transitive verb.

جاء بالكتاب - bring the book

ذهب بالكتاب - to take away the book

¹ Qodirov.T.Sh.,Aliyev.D.I.Arab tili leksikologiyasi-Toshkent,2010

² IbrohimovI.,YusupovM. Arab tili grammatikasi1,Namangan-2009,b-212

وصل بالخبر - to bring news

رجع بالبشرى - to return with good news

There are also some such intransitive verbs with which the instrumental complement or case comes in the accusative agreement.

ركب السيارة - Getting into the car

دخل الغرفة - To enter the room

سال المعلم - To ask the teacher

When the verb دخل is used in the sense of approaching someone, the preposition على is used after this verb. For example, دخل على العميد - to enter the presence of the dean

If the verb دخل is used for a place, then it is written without a preposition.

For example, دخلت البيت , I entered the house , هو دخل الغرفة - دخل -

If the verb دخل is not used for a place, then it comes with the preposition في. For example, verses 29-30 of Surah "Fajr" in the Holy Qur'an:

"فادخلي في عبادي"³ - So enter into my servants!

"وادخلي جنتي"⁴ - And enter my paradise!

In the first case, the verb دخل does not mean a place, but in the second case, it means a place. We can see such situations in Surah Hujurot-14 verse, Surah Insan-31 verse, Surah Nasr-2 verse and other verses.

From the above examples, we can see that in Arabic, action verbs are used together with prepositions, and this preposition causes a certain amount of change in the meaning of the verb. We can find many such examples in the Arabic language.

³ Qur'oni Karim-Fajr surasi-29 oyat Alouddin Mansur. Qur'oni Karim. – Toshkent : « Cho'lpon », 1992

⁴ Qur'oni Karim-Fajr surasi-30 oyat Alouddin Mansur. Qur'oni Karim. – Toshkent : « Cho'lpon », 1992

METHODOLOGY

Semantic analysis, and classification methods and analysis methods were widely used in this scientific work to find the correct solution to the goal.

The effect of the addition of the accusative ratio is great in the emergence of the meaning of active action in verbs. In many cases, this addition creates an action sense in case-based verbs: laugh (action verb) - laugh (action verb); This gives rise to the causativeness typical of the verbs of sense in linguistics. The object valence of action verbs is fundamentally different from the object valence of state verbs. Because object valence and causativeness occur on the basis of the object acting of state verbs, but this is not the case with action verbs.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

"The verb expresses a specific behavior, and this behavior belongs to the owner or to some event." Dr. Mustafa Jamoliddin says: "In my opinion, the phrase to happen represents the symbolic meaning of the word verb. Also, this phrase is somewhat close to the meaning of renewal, change."

One of the famous Arab linguists, Hifni Nasif, in his work "Ad-durus an-Nahwiya" gives the following definition of the verb: "Each word denoting the time of action is called a verb. The verb is divided into three parts: past tense, present tense, imperative tense. For example: he wrote, he is writing, write!"

A verb indicating that an action happened in the past is called a past tense verb.

About verbs of action, عماد عبد الرحمن خليل شلبي, الكلية للانسان في القران الكريم دراسة دلالة, in the scientific study "احصائية" الحركة دراسة الافعال الحركية الماضية في, دوكتور مالك يحيى, دوكتور كمال and افعال الحركة في ديوان من الاطلس" in the work of "سورة البقرة" واجهة by حركة الفعل ودلالة" دراسة اسلوبية في كافوريات المتنبى" عبد الرزاق صالح اللسانيت الادراكية "اتى" اللسانيت الادراكية "اتى" نموذجاً" افعال الركة في القران الكريم من واجهة افعال في القران " as well as , حدائق رضائي - ناديا دادبور , سيد محمد رضا ابن الرسول - نموذجاً"

دوكتور بريهي شياح دوكتور بريهي شياح الثويني of الكريم و دلالاتها في السياق القراني حرف الاف" and the work : "دلالة افعال الحركة في اطار المعجم المولد" : الثويني the verbs of action were also analyzed.

"In the development of any language, its most changing and fastest moving part is its lexicon"⁵, so studying this area in linguistics is one of the most important issues at all times.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Imad Abdurahman Halil Shalabi in his master's dissertation "Study of verbs of human direction in the Holy Qur'an and their semantics"⁶ divides the types of verbs in the Qur'an into 13 groups according to their meaning. (see table 1)

Table1.

13 types of verbs in the Qur'an

Nº	Types	In Arabic
1.	Action verbs that mean moving forward	اتى, اقبل, جاء, حضر, قدم, ورد, جاس,) اقتحم
2.	Action verbs that mean going back	هلم, تعال, انقلب, ناب, رجع, ادبر, ولى, عاد, خلف, رد, قفي
3.	Verbs of action meaning to prohibit, block, destroy	اسر, حشر, حصر, ساق
4.	Verbs of movement in the direction of rotation	طاف, حخ, اعتمر
5.	Action verbs with the meaning of exit and departure	بعث, ارسل, طرد, صرف, خرج, سار, مشى, مضى, ذهب, جاوز, سلك, غدا

⁵ O'zbek tili leksikologiyasi.-Toshkent.: Fan,1981.-4-bet

⁶ 2010 - عماد عبد الرحمن خليل شلبي افعال الحركة الانتقالية الكلية للانسان في القرآن الكريم دراسة دلالة احصائية

6.	Verbs with the meaning of expansion	هاجر, فارق, انفض, انفر, سرح, ضرب, انتشار, وضع
7.	Verbs of action meaning to arrive somewhere	وصل, بلغ, تبغ, لحق
8.	Action verbs in the meaning of acceleration and running	ركض, سابق, سارع, سعى, انطلق, تعجل, فر, زف
9.	Action verbs meaning slow movement	فسح, زحزح, درج
10.	Action verbs in the sense of entering a place	دخل, هبط, ركب, لقي, غرق
11.	Action verbs in the sense of meeting	صحب, زار, لقي
12.	Action verbs in the sense of moving up	صعد, رفع
13.	Action verbs related to specific situations	خاض, اسرى, نجا

In his dissertation, Imad Abdurahman Halil Shalabi described that many verbs of movement in the Holy Qur'an, which give the meaning of the direction of a person, have a clear meaning of moving forward. He also said that the action verbs in the Holy Qur'an are generally related to prophets, and in particular, we can find many verbs with this meaning in the Surahs of Yusuf and Ibrahim. Some action verbs are associated with a certain class of people, for example, Muslims, infidels. And at the same time, he explained that these verbs have two meanings, that is, to warn the polytheists and to give good news to Muslims. In the Holy Qur'an, verbs of action express that they are carried out only in a certain place and in a certain time. For example, the verb **غدا** the meaning of the verb **غدا** is to set out

early in the morning, to set off in the morning, and this verb indicates that the action is carried out in the morning. And the verb غرق – to sink is a verb that is used with water. In some verses, verbs of action in the Holy Qur'an represent human action verbs, while in some verses, it is the opposite. For example, the verb اتى can be associated with a person or death. When it comes to a person, the object of action is a person. When it comes in connection with death, it comes in a figurative sense. Some verbs express the meaning of a person's unwillingness, and some verbs express the meaning of the purity of a person's will. These verbs are related to certain classes of people. In the Holy Qur'an, the speed of human movement is limited by certain verbs.⁷

CONCLUSION

In general, there are two opposing sides in the system of forming words from verbs in the Arabic language, one of which is to perform an action for oneself (self) and to focus on an object or action-action itself. It means that the object itself performs (inaction). The morphological indicator of identity is the element "ت". There are intensive and extensive aspects that form the basis of the verb, and they mean the strengthening of the action and its repeated occurrence, the mutual performance of the action. The analysis of action verbs in the Uzbek language shows their general and specific aspects were determined, while in Arabic some action verbs are associated with a certain class of people, and at the same time, these verbs have two meanings, that is, to warn the polytheists and to give good news to Muslims. The verbs of action express that they are carried out only in a certain place and in a certain time.

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